

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF THE CONCEPT OF TOLERANCE

A. Salokhov

BukhMTI, associate professor of the Department of Social Sciences

G.A. Qamariddinova

Teacher of the Department of Social Sciences

ABSTRACT

The article aims to reveal ways of pedagogical support for the young generation to be free from defects in the qualities of tolerance and tolerance, especially in the field of human relations, when they enter the scene of the world community. In order to understand the essence of tolerance, first of all, it is necessary to analyze the types of it and the relationship between them. It is impossible to achieve the intended goal if we try to cultivate religious or ethnic tolerance and forget about other types. Therefore, it is stated that a comprehensive approach is considered important in the formation and development of tolerance in the literal sense.

Keywords: Tolerance, youth, justice, honesty, religion, faith, faith, humanity, truthfulness.

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОСНОВАНИЕ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ

А.Салохов

БухМТИ, доцент кафедры социальных наук

Камариддинова Г.А.

преподаватель кафедры социальных наук

АННОТАЦИЯ

Целью статьи является раскрытие путей педагогической поддержки молодого поколения, свободного от дефектов качеств толерантности и толерантности, особенно в сфере человеческих отношений, когда они выходят на арену мирового сообщества. Чтобы понять сущность толерантности, прежде всего, необходимо проанализировать ее виды и взаимосвязь между ними. Невозможно достичь намеченной цели, если мы попытаемся воспитать

религиозную или этническую толерантность и забыть о других типах. Поэтому констатируется, что важным в формировании и развитии толерантности в прямом смысле считается комплексный подход.

Ключевые слова: Толерантность, молодежь, справедливость, честность, религия, вера, вера, человечность, правдивость.

BAG‘RIKENGLIK TUSHUNCHASINING IJTIMOIIY-FALSAFIY VA PEDOGOGIK ASOSLARI

A. Saloxov

BuxMTI Ijtimoiy fanlar kafedrası dotsenti,

G.A. Qamariddinova

Ijtimoiy fanlar kafedrası o‘qituvchisi

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada yosh avlodning dunyo hamjamiyati sahnasiga kirib borishida, ayniqsa, insoniy munosabatlar doirasida kutilmagan muammolarga, jumladan, bag‘rikenglik, tolerantlik fazilatlarda nuqsondan xoli bo‘lishlariga pedagogik madad yo‘llarini ochib berishdan iborat. Bag‘rikenglikning mohiyatini chuqurroq anglash uchun, avvalo uning qanday turlari mavjudligi va ular o‘rtasidagi aloqa-dorligini tahlil qilish lozim. Diniy yoki etnik bag‘rikenglikni tarbiyalashga zo‘r berib, boshqa turlarini unutib qo‘yilsa, ko‘zlangan maqsadga erishish mumkin emas. Shuning uchun tom ma‘nodagi bag‘rikenglikni shakllantirish va rivojlantirishda kompleks yondashish muhim hisoblanishi bayon qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Bag‘rikenglik, yoshlar, adolat, insof, diyonat, iymon, e‘tiqod, insonparvarlik, haqiqatparvarlik.

In world science, scientific and theoretical research is being conducted to study the content, essence, goals and tasks of historical memory, processes of global importance. In particular, issues of preserving our values, passing them on to the next generation, restoring historical memory have become the main research directions of scientific institutions.

That is why it is necessary to constantly strengthen the moral basis of education and enrich it with the heritage of ancestors. If we need happiness, dignity, peace, stability, pleasure, honor, honor and attention, we should learn the methods of raising the next generation as soon as possible and educate our children based on these methods and rules.

It is to reveal ways of pedagogical support for the young generation entering the scene of the world community, especially in the field of human relations, to avoid unexpected problems, including tolerance and tolerance. In order to understand the essence of tolerance, first of all, it is necessary to analyze the types of it and the relationship between them. It is impossible to achieve the intended goal if we try to cultivate religious or ethnic tolerance and forget about other types. Therefore, it is important to take a comprehensive approach to the formation and development of true tolerance.

In the social encyclopedic dictionary: "Tolerance is the management principle of social work, recognition of cultural, racial and other differences between individuals, groups and social communities, regarding the differences in people's appearance, behavior, value orientation and their differences. "Tolerance is being tolerant of other people's way of life, behavior, habits, feelings, opinions, ideas and beliefs." it is said.

Pedagogically scientific-theoretical study of tolerance thinking and culture, introducing it to all stages of the education system, and understanding its pedagogic foundations have begun. Developing tolerance in young people, we considered it appropriate to first analyze the content of the category of tolerance. From a pedagogical point of view, tolerance is "a form or expression of human tolerance, which means the absence or weakness of a firm response to a factor that is unpleasant for a person. No matter how much a person does not like that situation or factor, he tolerates it, calms down, adapts if necessary."

Today, there is a need to reform higher education institutions in our country based on the experience of developed countries. In such a situation, it is necessary to educate students who meet world standards by increasing their knowledge, outlook, and thinking.

Due to the lack of tolerance, there are frequent cases of attracting people to different religious movements, causing religious conflicts, destroying the cultural monuments of this or that nation, destroying the people's pride and national wealth. In the education of tolerance, it is recommended to apply pedagogical measures, determining the individuality, originality, tendency to master the concepts of tolerance, and the level of habituation to creative thinking of each student. Otherwise, the possibilities of pedagogical influence will not be manifested.

As part of the description, it should be noted that the model of the formation of the tolerance mindset, regardless of its content and direction, requires the integration of all pedagogical methods and methods of the formation of the culture of tolerance. Based on their capabilities, each educational institution will develop methods of creating a culture of tolerance. If you look at the main methods and system of methods

for forming a culture of tolerance among young people, you will be sure of the wide range of possibilities.

The word "tolerance" was originally used in the fields of biology and medicine, and this term was applied to people who do not have immunity. Tolerance was not understood by different cultures as a concept and depended on the historical experience of the communities. Although the concept of tolerance is interpreted differently in the languages of different peoples and nations of the world, its essence remains almost unchanged. As a result of our research, it would be appropriate to classify this concept as follows. The dictionary meanings of terms describing tolerance in several languages of the world are as follows:

In English, "tolerance" means unquestioning acceptance of a person or a reality;

- in French - to be attentive to the political or religious way of thinking and views of others;

- and in Arabic sources - grace is used in the meanings of forgiveness, mercy, patience;

- in the Chinese language, it means to be kind to the actions of others, to show tolerance towards others;

- In the explanatory dictionaries of Russia - tolerance is interpreted in the meaning of tolerance. Studying religious and national tolerance and instilling it in the minds and hearts of people, especially our youth, has always been one of the main tasks of science.

"Interreligious tolerance means that representatives of different religious confessions live together in harmony for good goals and intentions, and work for the development of human society."

Professor Z. Kadirova defined the concept of tolerance and drew attention to the philosophical-physical-ethical nature of "tolerance" in the languages of the world's nations. For example, in Arabic explanatory dictionaries, the term "tasammul" is interpreted as patience, compassion, forgiveness, kindness, kindness, mercy, and gentleness. In Uzbek explanatory dictionaries, "tolerance" means the ability to accept another culture. In Russian sources, "tolerance" means to be calm, the ability to endure, to be patient, tenacious, to consider the opinions of others.

Indeed, during the years of independence, great work was done to restore our national and religious values. At the same time, in the conditions of our independence, they use the opportunity to restore our religion for their own despicable purposes, undermine the existing inter-religious tolerance, look disdainfully at our religious and national values inherited from our ancestors, and create instability in our country. moving forces and various currents also entered. In such conditions, the implementation of the important tasks, especially the implementation of the decisions

and decrees set by our government in the field of education, is an urgent issue for science:

a) restoring our religious and national values inherited from our ancestors, inculcating them in the minds and hearts of our youth;

b) based on the presence of believers of different religions and religious confessions in our country, creating conditions for their activities and consistently strengthening tolerant relations between them;

c) There is a need to fight against various political forces and evil religious currents aimed at creating instability in our country using the religious factor. At the same time, strengthening the independence of our country and its sustainable development by implementing these tasks, the development of inter-religious tolerance was objectively placed on the agenda.

Building a culture of tolerance is a complex process, and its effectiveness may have different indicators in different regions. However, the general result is that it is necessary to educate young students in the spirit of tolerance and to inculcate in their minds the sincere application of concepts such as compatriots and compatriots to all nations and peoples who live in the space called Motherland. For this, it is necessary to seriously monitor the behavior related to tolerance and give them a vital meaning in the daily activities of pedagogues.

In the new Uzbekistan, we can understand that all spheres, especially the reform of spiritual-educational-physical changes to the society, further increasing the social activity of our youth, and the problems of tolerance are an issue at the level of our government's policy. The national-historical traditions related to the setting and solving of these problems with modern conditions and factors were also defined. At the same time, the problems of tolerance among young people have a special place in our historical-philosophical heritage.

In our opinion, in order to educate young people in the spirit of tolerance in the process of education and training, in the system of higher and secondary special education, it is necessary to carry out activities based on the improved complex that includes all the features of the formation of a "perfect person", to enable young people to live in modern societies. Accepting the principles of tolerance as one of the main features of teaching, the full meaning of the concept of tolerance, the ability of a person to enter into interpersonal and inter-community relations based on the logical coherence and moral integrity of the principles of tolerance, to correctly come out of various situations and clearly summarize problems based on tolerance should educate such qualities.

REFERENCES:

1. Azimov, A. A., & Avliyokulov, U. M. (2019). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ЭПОХИ АБУ АБДУЛЛАХ РУДАКИ. Theoretical & Applied Science, (5), 560-562.
2. Темиров, Ш. Т., & Азимов, А. А. (2016). Экономический и культурный рост народов центральной азии в IX-X веках. In Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества (pp. 104-105).
3. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). Политическая и социальная жизнь в бухарском эмирате во взглядах ахмада дониша. In Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества (pp. 66-67).
4. Azimov, A. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL AND ETHICAL IDEAS OF THE EARLY RENAISSANCE OF THE EAST IN CENTRAL ASIA AND THEIR REFLECTION IN THE VIEWS OF ZAKARIA AR RAZI. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(7), 57-62.
5. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). КУЛЬТУРНАЯ И АРХИТЕКТУРНАЯ ВЗАИМОВЛИЯНИЯ ВОСТОКА И ВОСТОЧНОЙ ЕВРОПЫ С БУХАРОЙ. In Современные тенденции развития науки и производства (pp. 33-34).
6. Азимов, А. А. ўғли Рўзиев, АШ (2022, December). ОСОБЕННОСТИ КНИГИ АВЕСТА. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 37-42).
7. ВЗГЛЯДЫ РУДАКИ О ВОСПИТАНИИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА АА Азимов - Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2023 515-523
8. SCIENCE, LITERATURE AND POETRY IN TRANSOXIANA AND KHORASAN IX-X CENTURIES. АА Abdullayevich - MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE, 2023 247-260
9. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (2015). Дипломатические и торговые связи Бухары с Россией XVI–XVIII вв. Молодой учёный, 20, 548.
10. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (1994). Рабочая кооперация Узбекистана в 20-е-начале 30-х гг.
11. Atoyev, J. H., & Saloxov, A. Q. (2022). KONSTITUTSIYADA OILA HUQUQI. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(TSTU Conference 2), 637-640.
12. Salokhov, A. Q. (2023). METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF USING THE IDEAS OF BUKHARA NOVELTY IN FORMING TOLERANCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(8), 171-178.
13. Салохов, А. К. К АНАЛИЗУ ИДЕЙ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ ТУРКЕСТАНСКОГО ДЖАДИДИЗМА В КОНТЕКСТЕ ЕЕ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА

МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ МИРЗО УЛУҒБЕК НОМИДАГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН МИЛЛИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ ФУҚАРОЛИК ЖАМИЯТИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИНИ МОНИТОРИНГ, 464.

14. Салохов, А. Қ. БУХОРО МАЪРИФАТПАРВАРЧИЛИГИНИНГ ТАРИХИЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ.

15. Murodov, S. A. (2022). Relationship between the universe and man in the works of Fariduddin Attor. In International conference: problems and scientific solutions (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 35-41).

16. Мурадов, С. А. Современные методы философии и их значение в развитии мышления человека. Актуальные исследования, 51.

17. Мурадов, С. А. (2009). Ибн Сино, Аттор ва Навоий асарларида кушлар тимсоли. Имом ал-Бухорий сабоқлари», Маънавий-маърифий, илмий-адабий журнал. Тошкент, 273-276.

18. Мурадов, С. А. кизи Касимова, ФФ (2022, December). ФИЛОСОФИЯ ДИЗАЙНА: ОСОБЕННОСТИ И СУЩНОСТЬ. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 51-59).

19. Санжар, М. (2020). Взгляды Фаридуддина Атгара на бытие. Международный журнал прикладных исследований. ИДЖАР, 6(6), 34-36.

20. МУРАДОВ, С. А. СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ФАРИДУДДИНА АТТОРА. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый, 51, 529-531.

21. Aslonovich, M. S., & Zaynura, M. (2023, June). NATIONAL DRESSES OF CENTRAL ASIA: AS A COMPONENT OF" CULTURE OF DESIGN". In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 170-177).

22. Aslonovich, M. S., & Zaynura, M. (2023, June). NATIONAL DRESSES OF CENTRAL ASIA: AS A COMPONENT OF" CULTURE OF DESIGN". In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 170-177).

23. Мурадов, С. А. (2023, June). ФАРИДУДДИН АТТОР-ВЕЛИКИЙ ШЕЙХ ВОСТОКА. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 149-160).

24. Muradov, S. A. (2023). THE MAIN IDEAS OF THE FOUNDER OF THE GERMAN SCHOOL OF PHILOSOPHY. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 588-594.

25. Sanjar, M. One of the Factors of Purity of the Heart is Futuwat. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 98-101.

26. Sanjar, M. (2020). The views of Fariduddin Attar on being. International journal of applied research. IJAR, 6(6), 34-36.
27. Nurmatova N. U. THE WORK “MAQOMOTI YUSUF HAMADONIY” BY ABDULKHOLIK GHIJDUVONIY—A SAMPLE OF RESPECT TO THE MASTER” //Central Asian Problems of Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 210-218.
28. Нурматова Н. У. ЮСУФ ҲАМАДОНИЙ ТОМОНИДАН ХОЖАГОН ТАЪЛИМОТИГА КИРИТИЛГАН БИРИНЧИ РАШҲА //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 565-576.
29. UMAROVNA, N. N. Four basis analysis of human perfection in the work of Yusuf Khamadani, Odobi tariqat. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 7(4), 1-3.
30. Nurmatova N. U. Logical analysis of Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani’s work “Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoni”/ISSN (Online): 2455-3662 EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)-Peer Reviewed Journal //Volume. – Т. 7. – С. 417-420.
31. Djuraev A. et al. Cotton increase the efficiency of cleaning as a result of improving the unit for cleaning small and large wastes //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing, 2023. – Т. 2789. – №. 1.
32. Нурматова, Нигора, and Нодиржон Сафоев. "ШКОЛА СУФИЗМА ЮСУФА ХАМАДОНИ В БУХАРЕ." INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE. Vol. 2. No. 15. 2023.
33. Нурматова Н. У. ЮСУФ ҲАМАДОНИЙ ТОМОНИДАН ХОЖАГОН ТАЪЛИМОТИГА КИРИТИЛГАН БИРИНЧИ РАШҲА //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 565-576.
34. Nurmatova, N. U. Logical analysis of Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani’s work “Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoni”/ISSN (Online): 2455-3662 EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)-Peer Reviewed Journal. Volume, 7, 417-420.
35. Nurmatova N. U. THE WORK “MAQOMOTI YUSUF HAMADONIY” BY ABDULKHOLIK GHIJDUVONIY—A SAMPLE OF RESPECT TO THE MASTER” //Central Asian Problems of Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 210-218.
36. Нурматова Н. У. Юсуф Ҳамадоний ва хожагон-нақшбандия таълимотининг “назар бар қадам” рашҳаси //Zamonaviy oliy ta’lim: muammo va yechimlar. Xalqaro ilmiy konferensiya. Navoiy. – 2022. – С. 30-31.
37. Jahongir, S. (2020). Philosophical views of Umar life. Academicia. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.—India, 10(4), 360-364.

38. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. *International engineering journal for research & development.-India*, 5(3), 143-148.
39. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Interpretation of the image of may in the ruba of Umar Khayyam. *Monografia pokonferencyjna science, research, development*, 33, 2020-30.
40. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём фалсафий қарашларида инсон тақдири ва эркин ирода масаласи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 2, 197-204.
41. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг асосий асарлари ва рубоийларининг тузилиши, мазмуни ва таҳлили. *Илм Сарчашмалари.-Урганч*, 10, 44-47.
42. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём рубоийларининг талқин ва тавсифи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 9, 206-210.
43. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг ижтимоий-ахлоқий қарашлари. *Фалсафа ва ҳуқуқ.-Тошкент*, 3, 107-110.
44. Shodiev, J. (2021). The problem of knowledge in the philosophical views of Umar Khayyam. *Imam al-Bukhari IBS Journal*, 2.
45. Шодиев, Ж. (2022). Илк уйғониш даврида–комил инсонни шакллантириш ватарбиялашда тасаввуф таълимотининг ўрни. *Scientific Bulletin of NamSU-Научный вестник НамГУ-NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi–2022-yil_4-сон*, 229.
46. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Мамлакатимизда инсон қадрини юксалтиришнинг ижтимоий-фалсафий масалалари. *Қарду хабарлари. Илмий-назарий, услубий журнал. Махсус сон (Ижтимоий фанлар)*.
47. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). INTERPRETATION AND DESCRIPTION OF UMAR KHAYYAM RUBAYA. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(9), 206-211.
48. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). AGAINST IGNORANCE-FIGHTING WITH ENLIGHTENMENT THE MAIN CRITERIA IN IMPROVING HUMAN VALUE. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(10), 1160-1164.
49. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). ATTITUDE TO HUMAN DIGNITY IN THE PERIOD OF AMIR TEMUR AND TEMURIDS DYNASTY. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(5), 43-47.
50. Shodiyev, J. (2021). JAMIYATDAGI MEHNAT MUNOSABATLARI SHAROITIDA MA'NAVIY SALOHİYAT. *Журнал истории и общества*, (2)
51. SHODIEV, J. (2021). SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE IN THE PERIOD OF UMAR KHAYAM. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 1(1).

52. Shodiyev, J. (2021). O'ZBEKISTONDA IJTIMOIIY-SIYOSIY KOMMUNIKATSIYA RIVOJLANISHIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SIYOSATI. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(2), 409-416.
53. Shodiyev, J. J. (2020). U THE QUESTION OF HUMAN DESTINY AND FREE IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF OMAR KHAYYAM. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(2), 197-202.
54. Shodiev Jahongir Jurakulovich. Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development 2020/4/16.
55. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). The role of the national idea in increase of human values. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(10), 1160-1164.
56. Shodiyev Jahongir Jo'raqulovich. Inson qadri va uning huquqlari eng oliy qadriyat: tarixiy-huquqiy meros. Ilm sarchashmalari/ Urganch – 3.2023. 19-21.
57. Shodiyev, J. J. (2023). THE ROLE OF SCIENTIFIC THINKING AND MENTAL DEVELOPMENT IN IMPROVING HUMAN DEVELOPMENT AND VALUE. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(9), 251-261.
58. Shodiyev, J. J. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NATIONAL IDEA IN INCREASE OF HUMAN VALUES. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 616-625.
59. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF SAGES ON HUMAN VALUES AND GLORIFYING HIM. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 2(16), 229-238.
60. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2023, June). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ В СОЗДАНИИ ФУНДАМЕНТА ТРЕТЬЕГО ВОЗРОЖДЕНИЯ И ЕГО ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В УКРЕПЛЕНИИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 124-130).
61. JJ Shodiev. [A STEP TOWARDS HUMAN DIGNITY](#). GOLDEN BRAIN 1 (24), 59-67.
62. Музафаровна, А.М. (2022). СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННАЯ РЕФОРМА И ВОЗНИКАЮЩИЕ КОНФЛИКТЫ. Международный междисциплинарный исследовательский журнал Galaxy , 10 (5), 623-626.
63. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2015). Интернационализация профессионального образования как требование времени. Молодой ученый, (2), 506-509.
64. Алимова, М. М. (2022, December). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННЕЙ МОТИВАЦИЕЙ РАБОТНИКОВ НА БЕЗОПАСНЫЙ ТРУД И ВЫПОЛНЕНИЕ

- ТРЕБОВАНИЙ ОХРАНЫ ТРУДА. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 43-50).
65. Muzafarovna, A. M., & Tangrievich, M. B. (2021). FORCED COLLECTIVIZATION OF AGRICULTURE IN ZARAFSHAN OASIS (1928-1932). Thematics Journal of Education, 6(November).
66. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2016). Перспективы использования технологии сотрудничества в процессе подготовки педагога профессионального образования. Молодой ученый, (12), 839-841.
67. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2016). Психологические основы педагогического проектирования. Молодой ученый, (12), 837-839.
68. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2015). Социально-психологические факторы формирования модели педагога в современном образовательном процессе. Молодой ученый, (2), 504-506.
69. Алимова, М. М. (2023). «РАСКРЕПОЩЕНИЕ» ЖЕНЩИН В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ (1920-1930 г. г). Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(8), 535-541.
70. Алимова, М. М., & Гариев, А. (2023). ПРОТИВОДЕЙСТВИЕ КОРРУПЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(24), 261-270.
71. Бафоев Ф. М. Историческая память в мировой политике. Роль ООН и других международных организаций //Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2017. – №. 1-4. – С. 180-182.
72. Бафоев Ф. М. ПРИНЦИП НЕДЕЛИМОСТИ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ //Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2018. – №. 1-1. – С. 51-54.
73. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. О ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ, РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПРОДОВОЛЬСТВЕННОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований". – №. 21. – С. 53-55.
74. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. К ВОПРОСУ КОРРЕКТИРОВКИ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ПОНЯТИЯ «МИРОВАЯ ПОЛИТИКА» В КОНТЕКСТЕ СИНЕРГЕТИКИ //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. – С. 31.
75. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. К вопросу о динамике современных международных отношений //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований",(20). – 2022. – С. 35-37.
76. Каримов, Б. (2011). Гармонизация взаимоотношений государства, общества и человека как основа справедливого общества. постановка вопроса. Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество, 8(1), 71-73.

77. Каримов, БК (2021). Гармония разума и духа. Американский журнал социальных наук и инноваций в образовании , 3 (05), 230–234.
78. Каримов, Б. (2023). ПРОЦЕССЫ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ В ДОКУМЕНТАХ ГЕНЕРАЛЬНОЙ АССАМБЛЕИ ООН (2017-2019). MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(24), 291-301.
79. Каримов, Б.К. (2023). СУЩНОСТЬ СОЗНАНИЯ И ЕГО ГЕНЕЗ. Инновационное развитие в образовательной деятельности , 2 (7), 532-539.
80. Aminovna, V. G. (2021). The role of social system and political ideas in achieving human prosperity. Thematics Journal of Education, 6(November).
81. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ПРАВОВАЯ И РЕЛИГИОЗНАЯ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ В СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ В ПЕРИОД ПЕРВОГО РЕНЕССАНСА ВОСТОКА. МОДЕЛИ И МЕТОДЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ , 2 (24), 271-279.
82. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ПРИОРИТЕТЫ МОЛОДЕЖНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 524-531.
83. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ЁШЛАРНИ БАҒРИКЕНГЛИК РУҲИДА ТАРБИЯЛАШДА ИЖТИМОЙ ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ҰРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 5(NUU Conference 2), 232-240.
84. Аминовна, Б. Г. (2022). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННИХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ПУТЕЙ СВЯЗИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОАЗИАТСКИХ КОРОЛЕВСТВ В РАЗВИТИИ ТОРГОВЛИ. Web of Scientist: Международный научный исследовательский журнал, 3, 10-12.
85. Шукриллаев, Ю. А. (2006). Бухоро амирлигида кўшин ва ғарбий иш (1756-1920 йиллар). Тарих фанлари номзоди илмий дражасини олиш учун езилган диссертация.
86. Шукуруллаев, Ю. (2022, December). СОЗДАНИЕ ВОЕННЫХ УСТАВНЫХ ГРУПП ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО ТИПА В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ. In "INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS" (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 42-51).
87. Шукруллаев, Ю. А. Армия Бухарского эмирата и военное дело (1756-1920 гг.). Автореферат кандидатской диссертации по истории.-Ташкент, 2006.-26 с.; К вопросу о дипломатических сношениях между Россией и Бухарой через Оренбург в конце XVIII-начале XIX веков. Общественные науки в Узбекистане.- 1962, 7, 55-59.
88. Shukrullayev, Y. A. The Army of Bukhara Emirate and Military Affairs (1756-1920). Synopsis of candidate dissertation in history.-Tashkent, 2006.-26 pp.; On the

Issue of Diplomatic Relations between Russia and Bukhara through Orenburg at the End of the XVIII-th-the Beginning of the XIX-th Centuries. Social Sciences in Uzbekistan.-1962, 7, 55-59.

89. Shukrullayev, Y. A., & Bahritdinovna, S. R. (2023). GERMANIYA FEDERATIV RESPUBLIKASI IQTISODIYOTINI TIKLASH HARAKATI.“IQTISODIY MO ‘JIZA”. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 577-587.

90. Shukrullayev, Y. A. (2022). FRANSIYA–O ‘ZBEKISTON ALOQALARINING TARIXIY ILDIZLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 1(3), 110-113.

91. Шукурллаев, Ю. (2023). ВОЕННЫЕ РЕФОРМЫ В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ ПОД ПРОТЕКТОРАТОМ. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 2(16), 249-260.

92. Шукурллаев, Ю. А. (2023). БУХОРО АМИРЛИГИДА ҚЎШИН ТАРКИБИГА ҚАБУЛ ҚИЛИШ ҚОИДАЛАРИ, АСКАРЛАРНИНГ ҚЎШИН ТАРКИБИДАН ҚОЧИШИ (ДЕЗЕРТИРСВО), САБАБИ ВА ОҚИБАТЛАРИ. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(8), 513-524.

93. Shukurillayev, Y. (2023). Sherbachus and Afghan Groups in the Emirate of Bukhara. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal, 2(1), 34-36.

94. Sultanova, L. (2021). The historical roots of spiritual education of youth. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 461-463.

95. Mavlonova, I., Akhmetjanov, M., Vokhidova, M., Fayziev, S., & Shokirova, S. (2022, December). Experimental studies of the dynamics of the proposed design of the presser foot with an additional conical spring. In Journal of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 2373, No. 2, p. 022047). IOP Publishing.

96. Vohidova, M. (2023). SOCIAL AND ETHICAL ASPECTS OF THE EXISTENCE OF TOLERANCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(6), 559-566.

97. Вахидова, М. Т., & Мирзаев, У. Т. (2022, December). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ КУЛЬТУРЫ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS" (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 52-62).

98. Вахидова, М. Т. (2022). ДУХОВНО-ПРАВСТВЕННОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ МОЛОДЕЖИ УЗБЕКИСТАН В КОНТЕКСТЕ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(7), 82-90.

99. Султонова, Л. С. (2023). ИЖТИМОЙ-ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАРНИ ЎҚИТИШДА ПЕДАГОГИК ИННОВАЦИЯ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН

ФАОЛИЯТНИНГ УЗВИЙЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 5(NUU Conference 2), 633-639.

100. Sultonova, L. (2023). Upbringing Mature Person. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 4(3), 71-73.

101. Султанова, Л. С. (2023). ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ПОДРОСТОЯЩЕГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(7), 557-564.

102. Султанова, Л. С. (2022). МЕСТО ИНЖЕНЕРНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ В ПОДГОТОВКЕ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ. YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 1(6), 29-34.